

Severe tympanic bullae pathology in a pregnant Minke whale *Balaenoptera acutorostrata* Lacépède, 1804 stranded near Texel, The Netherlands

Hidde Bakker^{1*}, Pierre Bonnet², Adrie Vonk², and Jeroen P.A. Hoekendijk²

¹ Natural History Museum Rotterdam, Westzeedijk 345, 3015 AA Rotterdam, The Netherlands

² Ecomare, Ruijslaan 92, 1796 AZ De Koog, Texel, The Netherlands;

* Correspondence: hiddecbakker@hotmail.com (H.B.)

ABSTRACT

This paper describes a case of pathology in the tympanic bullae of an adult common Minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata* Lacépède, 1804) found stranded on the beach of Razende Bol, a sandbar located near the southernmost point of the Dutch Wadden island of Texel, The Netherlands. The female whale appeared to have been in good physical condition at the time of death, as indicated by a substantial blubber layer and the presence of a near-term fetus. The tympanic bullae, along with osteological abnormalities of the left flipper, are systematically examined and described. In addition, the fetal skeletal remains were analysed to estimate the stage of gestation at the time of death. Several differential diagnosis and hypotheses are proposed to explain the origin of the observed pathologies, offering potential insights into degenerative auditory conditions in baleen whales.

Keywords Cetacea, Baleen whale, Tympanic bulla, *Balaenoptera acutorostrata*, Pathology, Wadden islands, Case report.

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Author for correspondence

hiddecbakker@hotmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

The common Minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata* Lacépède, 1804) represents the smallest baleen whale species inhabiting the Southern North Sea (Camphuysen & Peet 2006). Although relatively common in these waters, comprehensive anatomical studies of stranded individuals remain comparatively scarce. Such investigations are important for understanding the range of morphological variation and occurrence and nature of pathological conditions that may affect their skeleton.

The tympanic bullae in cetaceans aids their perception of sound to a greater extent compared to land-based mammals and exhibits an array of functional modifications. In most mammals, the tympanic membrane (eardrum) converts airborne sound waves into mechanical vibrations. These vibrations are transmitted through the auditory ossicles – the malleus, incus, and stapes – which convey them to the oval window of the cochlea. Within the cochlea, the resulting pressure waves move through its fluid, stimulating hair cells. These sensory cells then transduce the mechanical movements

into nerve impulses that are interpreted by the brain. Since cetaceans rarely deal with air borne sounds, the first step of this process involves a highly modified tympanic bulla which is physically as well as acoustically more isolated from the skull compared to terrestrial mammals. The involucrum (thickened inner lip of the tympanic bulla) replaces the tympanic membrane function in cetaceans and as such the malleus is directly fused to the tympanic bulla's outer lip thereby transferring its vibrations more effectively to the remaining auditory ossicles. The tympanic bullae thus serve an important resonating function that enhances sound perception. Nevertheless, bone conduction of sound through the skull to the cochlea remains present and is functionally more pronounced in baleen whales (*Mysticeti*) due to stronger cranial connections, compared to toothed whales (*Odontoceti*). Not only the involucrum portion of the tympanic bullae but also the surrounding bony connections enhance sound transmission and so aid perception. Acoustic impedance, the bilateral asymmetry in auditory reception time between the left and right ear and the vibrating response of the tympanic bullae, is crucial for directional hearing although the mechanism resulting in directional hearing in baleen whales is not well understood (Cranford *et al.* 2025; Morris *et al.* 2025).

Despite the functional importance of the tympanic bullae, healed fractures have been reported with notable frequency. Turner, 1912 and Van Deirse, 1938 described fractured tympanic bullae of the Blue whale *Balaenoptera musculus* (Linnaeus, 1758). Yamato *et al.*, 2015 added five species with similar fractures: Fin whale *Balaenoptera physalus* (Linnaeus, 1758), Sei whale *Balaenoptera borealis* Lesson, 1828, Minke whale *B. acutorostrata*, Common dolphin *Delphinus delphis* Linnaeus, 1758 and Baird's beaked whale *Berardius bairdii* (Stejneger, 1883). This report is the second report describing pathological changes in the tympanic bullae of *B. acutorostrata* and differs from Yamato *et al.* (2015) in that the pathology is osteolytic rather than traumatic in origin. Such degenerative changes have historically received less scientific attention, yet they may provide valuable insights into auditory function, life history, and potential internal or environmental stress factors in this species.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Material

The described specimens are housed at Naturalis Biodiversity Centre (NBC, Leiden, The Netherlands) and bear the collection numbers RMNH.5070317a for the adult skeleton and RMNH.5070317b for the fetus.

The anatomical terminology follows Ekdale *et al.* (2011) and Mead & Fordyce (2009).

Measurements were recorded with callipers. Photographs were taken with a Canon EOS 70D(W) and 60mm zoom lens and subsequently processed using image-editing software such as GIMP – GNU.

For comparative purposes, the extensive cetological collection of the Natural History Museum Rotterdam (NMR) was examined, and the following specimens attributed to *B. acutorostrata* were studied: NMR999000003537 (periotic and tympanic bulla), NMR999000003535

(tympanic bulla), NMR999000003536 (tympanic bulla), NMR999000003410 (skull), NMR999000003024 (skull), NMR999000003013 (skull), NMR999000001543 (cervicals), NMR999000002604 (humerus), NMR999000002818 (ulna).

Specimen preparation

Necropsy was performed by an expert team in collaboration with Utrecht University (UU) and the Erasmus Medical Centre (EMC) and registered with case no. BA2 (at UU) and BA151215 (at EMC). Analyses of gastric and intestinal contents were conducted to determine dietary constituents and assess the presence of parasitic organisms at Wageningen Marine Research (WMR).

The skeleton was prepared by dissection, warm water maceration with temperatures between 35 and 40 degrees Celsius and degassing steps using ammonia.

Institutional abbreviations

EMC – Erasmus Medical Centre, Rotterdam, The Netherlands.

NBC – Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden, The Netherlands.

NMR – Natuurhistorisch Museum Rotterdam, Rotterdam, The Netherlands.

RMNH – Rijksmuseum van Natuurlijke Historie, Leiden, The Netherlands (now part of NBC).

UU – University Utrecht, Utrecht, The Netherlands.

WMR – Wageningen Marine Research, Wageningen, The Netherlands.

RESULTS

Systematics

Order Cetacea Brisson, 1762

Suborder Mysticeti Cope, 1891

Family Balaenopteridae Gray, 1864

Genus *Balaenoptera* Lacépède, 1804

Species *acutorostrata* (species complex) Lacépède, 1804

Description

General

RMNH.5070317a – Skeleton of adult *B. acutorostrata*

RMNH.5070317a is the skeleton of a female *B. acutorostrata* with a measured body length of 880 cm, found dead on December 12th 2015 at the sandbar "Razende Bol/Noorderhaaks" N 52° 58' 245" and E 040° 40' 118" in an advanced decomposed state (Fig 1, 2). Although this limited thorough investigation of soft tissues, the animal appeared to be in good nutritional condition at the time of death. This is supported by the presence of a thick blubber layer, the recovery of uneroded otoliths from 55 individual Herring (*Clupea harengus* Linnaeus, 1758) in the gastric contents -indicating recent feeding-, a well-filled intestine containing brownish, fatty material and a nearly full term pregnancy.

Two parasitic taxa were identified during necropsy: *Bolbosoma balaenae* (Gmelin, 1790), present in the intestine, and *Penella balaenopterae* Koren & Danielssen, 1877, observed on the skin in association with a minor lesion.

The skull is complete; however, the right squamosal is broken

Fig 1. Map indicating the sandbar 'De Razende Bol' the stranding location of a pregnant *B. acutorostrata* (RMNH.5070317a) during 2015.

off, exposing the cranial cavity. The salvage team reported that this damage occurred during extraction of the carcass from the sandbar, likely due to uneven external pressure applied to the skull.

RMNH.5070317b – Skeleton of a fetal *B. acutorostrata*

The specimen was recovered from the uterus of RMNH.5070317a during necropsy. Its body length was estimated at 2 meters. All skeletal elements are present with the exception of two posterior chevron bones. All elements are well developed, although small because of its juvenile status and furthermore lacking ankylosis of joint surfaces by the past presence of chondral epiphyseal plates. The skull, when put back together, has a condylobasal length of 444 mm

Measurements	Result in mm
Maximum length	438
Dorsoventral height of mandible 2 cm from the apex	36
Distance between the ventral margin of the mandible and maximum height of coronoid process	64
Diameter of mandibular foramen	19
Dorsoventral height of condyle	55

Table 1 Measurements of the mandible of the fetal *B. acutorostrata* RMNH.5070317b

Fig 2. The stranded pregnant *B. acutorostrata* (RMNH.5070317a) photographed by Sytske Dijkse.

Fig 3. Right mandible of RMNH.5070317b, the fetus of RMNH.5070317a.

Fig 4. Severely osteolytic tympanic bullae of *B. acutorostrata* (RMNH.5070317a). The right tympanic bulla: **A.** ventral, **B.** dorsal, **C.** medial and **D.** lateral views and left tympanic bulla: **E.** ventral, **F.** dorsal, **G.** medial and **H.** lateral views.

Fig 5. Normal tympanic bulla of *B. acutorostrata* (NMR 9990-3410) compared to the affected tympanic bullae of *B. acutorostrata* (RMNH.5070317a).

and does not possess any evidence of alveoli on the ventral portion of the maxilla. The bizygomatic width could not be taken due to some deformation of the cranial bones during the drying process. Lanzetti (2019) examined the ontogeny of *B. acutorostrata*, providing detailed correlations between osteological development and morphometric parameters. The mandible of the fetal specimen (RMNH.5070317b), measuring 438 mm in maximum length, was compared with this dataset (Fig 3, Table 1). Based on these correlations, the specimen corresponds to a gestational age of approximately 8-9 months. The estimated total body length indicates a comparable gestational stage. Consequently, the adult female (RMNH.5070317a) reached the final trimester of her pregnancy before her untimely death.

Tympanic bullae of adult *B. acutorostrata* RMNH.5070317a (Fig 4, Fig 5)

The right tympanic bulla is well enough preserved to measure its greatest length (117 mm, taken from the ventral side) which is within the range expected for of *B. acutorostrata* (Ekdale et al. 2011).

In ventral view three major and up to eight smaller defects

are distributed irregularly across its thin outer lip. Medially the outline of the main ridge is roughly preserved, and laterally the shallow and transversely orientated lateral furrow can be identified. Lateroposteriorly of the lateral furrow, the rather short and laterally pointing sigmoid process is present, followed by the conical process which ends 4 mm before a large posteriorly placed defect.

In dorsal view, the tympanic cavity appears most prominent due to the absence of the involucrum, which would overhang approximately 65% of this cavity in a normal anatomical configuration. The anterior lobe of the tympanic bulla is also severely affected with large openings in the thin outer lip (ventral facing surface), deforming the anterior outline. The posterior lobe exhibits the same large defect, which can also be seen from ventral view. Medially of the base of the anterior pedicle, a rugose area is present extending in posterior direction to the level of the tall, convex and well-developed conical process. The sigmoid process is unaffected and shows a prominent malleolar ridge running in anteromedial direction and a preserved facet for the malleus.

In medial view, two large pathological openings on the ventral side almost separate the section of the main ridge of the

Fig 6. Irregular bony proliferation affecting the left humerus, ulna and radius of *B. acutorostrata* (RMNH.5070317a) leading to ankylosis of the humerus-ulna joint. **A.** Humerus, ulna and radius with severe ankylosis of the humerus-ulna joint, **B.** extra skeletal bone segment near the humerus-radius joint in lateral view (upper) and medial view (lower), **C.** degenerative aspect of proximal radius articular surface with erosion and cavities medially on the articular surface and irregular exostosis at its lateral edges.

remaining the thin outer lip. Only two bony connections near the midline prevent partition.

The lateral view again shows the defected anterior and posterior lobe, with most of the midsection of the thin outer lip preserved with a broad lateral furrow, prominent sigmoid process, strong and convex sigmoid fissure and tall conical process posteriorly running in a posterolateral direction.

In contrast to its counterpart, the left tympanic bulla still possesses most of the involucrum, yet most other structures are missing.

In ventral view the involucrum is visible because of the absence of the majority of the thin outer lip. Dorsally the transverse creases are prominently distributed over its posterior half. In medial view the main ridge and involucral ridge can be identified in contrast to its counterpart described above. The lateral view mostly shows the involucrum portion in the absence of the thin outer lip.

RMNH.5070317a – *Other osteological abnormalities of adult B. acutorostrata*

Besides the pathological tympanic bullae, the skeleton shows

a complete ankylosis of the right humerus-ulna joint and partial degeneration of the humerus-ulna joint with an extra skeletal bone segment near this joint (Fig 6). The condition is unilateral and left humerus, radius and ulna showed a completely normal morphology.

Tympanic bullae of the fetal specimen *B. acutorostrata* RMNH.5070317b

Like the other bones, both tympanic bullae (measured at the level of the main ridge in lateral view: length 72 mm) and periotics of RMNH.5070317b are macroscopically well developed and proportionally large relative to the skull (Fig 7). Their advanced development compared to fetuses of terrestrial mammals highlights the functional significance of the auditory system as the primary sensory modality in cetaceans (Cozzi et al., 2012).

Tissue samples

Tissue samples of both RMNH.5070317a and RMNH.5070317b are present at NBC in multiple conservation variants (both ethanol and frozen), but were deemed unsuitable

Fig 7. Tympanic bulla of RMNH.5070317b, the fetus of RMNH.5070317a in **A.** ventral view, **B.** dorsolateral view.

for further disease related analysis due to the decomposition caused by the state of the specimen at the time of sample collection.

DISCUSSION

Evidence of past infections of RMNH.5070317a

It is safe to assume that the potency of infectious diseases depends on a multitude of aspects, of which the characteristics of the pathogen and the hosts immune status are important factors (Snieszko, 1974). The necropsy revealed no evidence suggestive of an active ear infection at the time of death. During preparation of the skeleton, extensive fibrotic tissues of the ear region, encasing the tympanic bullae, were reported (pers. comm. M. van Leeuwen 2025). These stiff fibrotic tissues typically form after active inflammation and can be present many years after the initial disease process. This observation supports that RMNH.5070317a did not suffer from an active ear infection close to the moment of death, but rather exhibited chronic structural changes indicative of a past infection.

The ankylosed humerus-ulna joint, olecranon of the ulna, proximal articular surface of the radius and extra skeletal bone formation all show small circular holes interpreted as cavities and fistulae suggestive of bacterial infection and the subsequent production of an exudate like pus (Kompanje, 1995; Kompanje, 1999). The bone segment might represent extra skeletal bone formation or a sequestrum, a segment of bone separated from its original skeletal element by osteomyelitis supporting the hypothesis that the left flipper was affected by a bacterial infection in the past (Goertz et al., 2011; Kompanje, 1995).

Hearing impairment in RMNH.5070317a

Although a detailed inspection of the ear region during necropsy was not performed, inspection of skeletal material on October 13th 2025 revealed that the stapes remained in situ and showed no visible signs of degeneration. The same

was true for the periotic bone, which exhibited an apparently intact architecture upon macroscopic examination. This raises the question of whether a baleen whale with severely pathological bullae is able to retain functional hearing when the auditory ossicles and cochlea remain unaffected. And if so, then possibly through sound perception via bone conduction through the skull. Tubelli et al. (2012) demonstrated that *B. acutorostrata* can detect frequency ranges of 100 Hz to 25 kHz when stimulated at the tympanic bulla, but 30 Hz to 7.5 kHz when stimulated at the glove finger, an epidermal outgrowth with a ligament attached to the first auditory ossicle (the malleus), which suggest that some perception of sound may remain in the absence of functional tympanic bullae. However, the auditory ossicles could not be examined in their entirety in RMNH.5070317, as the malleus and incus were missing and associated soft tissues were no longer preserved. It therefore remains uncertain whether the pathological tympanic bullae were the sole structures compromising the hearing ability of specimen RMNH.5070317a. As the involucrum is hypothesized to facilitate directional hearing in cetaceans, the best possible outcome is to assume that at least this function was hampered given the severity of osteolytic lesions of the tympanic bullae.

CONCLUSIONS

The tentative conclusions regarding the osteopathological changes observed in RMNH.5070317a;

- The poor status of the tympanic bullae may have been related to local and osteolytic (bacterial) infections earlier in life.
- A past bacterial infection of the right humerus–ulna–radius joint complex is considered the most likely explanation for the observed cavities and fistulae, and is interpreted as the result of a localized rather than systemic infection.

These findings reconfirm that baleen whales are capable of surviving extensive damage of the tympanic bullae, although

the functional impact of such injuries remain unclear. This study adds to the scientific body of knowledge that even reaching an extensive stage of pregnancy in good nutritional condition is possible for a baleen whale in the absence of functional tympanic bullae. Due to the advanced state of decomposition, it was not possible to further investigate the soft tissues of the ear region and surrounding fabric; therefore, it remains uncertain whether or not this Minke whale had completely lost the ability to hear.

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